
Academic Benefits of Noise-Cancelling Headphones

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SUMMARY

Putting Research into Practice:

Existing Knowledge:

1. Classroom noise disrupts cognition and academic performance, particularly for students with special needs.
2. Noise-cancelling (NC) headphones, both passive and active, are recommended to reduce auditory distractions.
3. Prior guidelines highlight their benefits but lack empirical support to validate these claims.

New Insights:

1. This scoping review identified 13 empirical studies, primarily involving students with special needs (e.g., ASD, ADHD, learning disabilities).
2. Results indicate benefits such as improved focus, reduced anxiety, and better task performance, especially for special needs students.
3. The evidence remains preliminary, with limited sample sizes, variability in outcomes, and lack of replication studies.

1. **Customized Use:** Provide NC headphones for students with sensory sensitivities or specific learning needs.
2. **Teacher Training:** Equip teachers with strategies to integrate NC headphones without stigmatization or dependency concerns.
3. **Policy Development:** Encourage research-backed policies to guide the use of NC headphones in classrooms.

Reference:

Kulawiak, P. R. (2021). Academic benefits of wearing noise-cancelling headphones during class for typically developing students and students with special needs: A scoping review. *Cogent Education*, 8(1), 1957530.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2021.1957530>

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